

D6.2 Report on Communication, Dissemination & Networking Activities v1

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Summary

INGUMA Project aims to foster the development of bio-based materials and their acceptance by the public by relying on three main values sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics - the values of the New European Bauhaus.

The value of sustainability will be tackled by developing different types of bio-based materials from raw materials derived from agriculture residues and secondary raw materials from wood processing. Various types of materials will be developed: functionalized fibers, insulation material based on mycelium, resin-free insulation material based on wood fibers, bio-based adhesive for plywood, low-formaldehyde plywood board, wooden sandwich panels, and growth media for plants. In addition, these materials will be integrated into insulation panels and vegetated roofs.

The sustainability and circularity of these materials and solutions will be ensured by applying environmental criteria and digital tools that will allow users to make decisions on the most sustainable solutions available. Additionally, the materials will be tested according to European and international standards, as a first step in the commercialization outside of Europe (Canada).

The value of inclusion will imply the design of co-creation laboratories that encourage collaboration among stakeholders, fostering transparent communication and generating innovative ideas. These labs will provide a platform for engagement and a structured process for stakeholders to contribute their insights and actively participate in the development of bio-based construction materials. This way, the acceptance of the developed materials, products and solutions by end-users and consumers will be maximized.

The value of aesthetics will be accomplished by co-designing and constructing a community house prototype in the rooftop of an experimental building (Derio, Spain) and as part of test houses (Savonlinna, Finland) that will use extensively the materials and products developed.

Executive Summary of the Deliverable

This deliverable summarises the communication, dissemination, and networking activities undertaken in the first 18 months of the INGUMA project, which promotes innovative bio-based materials aligned with the values of **sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics**, as defined by the **New European Bauhaus**.

Communication Activities

The communication strategy established INGUMA's core visibility and outreach tools. A cohesive **visual identity** was developed early, including a distinctive **logo**, the **Silka font** for graphical elements, and standardised templates for deliverables and presentations (see *Figure 1* and *Figure 5*).

A **mobile-optimised website** (www.inguma-biobased.eu), launched in M4 and updated in M9, serves as a central hub. Despite a modest dip in 2025 visits, key metrics remain strong:

- **Total visits:** 55,804 (2024–2025)
- **Unique visitors:** 3,010
(*Table 1: Website KPIs*)

On **LinkedIn**, INGUMA achieved **25,152 impressions**, with **794 reactions** and an above-average **24.5% engagement rate**, although the follower count (261) remains under target (*Figure 8*). A **six-page project brochure**, roll-ups, and posters have been developed and distributed sustainably, avoiding excess printing in line with EC guidelines (*Figure 10–11*).

Twelve blog articles and one press release covered general assemblies, workshops, and partner interviews, broadening the narrative reach (*Figure 13*).

Dissemination Activities

Dissemination was scaled up progressively, especially entering year two. Key highlights include:

- **Industrial dissemination** at major events:
 - **LIGNA 2025** (Hanover): Participation by CHIMAR and FNR, with co-creation workshops for the timber sector.
 - **EGURTEK 2024** (Bilbao): Panel presentation by BaskEgur.
 - **Drivers for Wood Construction 2025** (Finland): Presentation by LUKE.
(*Figures 14–16, Table 5: Event Participation Overview*)
- **Scientific dissemination** began with a **EURAXESS webinar** in collaboration with **Laval University (Canada)**, establishing an international academic link.
- **Policy dissemination** was initiated through participation in a **European Commission Cluster 6 workshop** in May 2025, contributing to policy discussions on bio-based innovation (*Figure 19*).

While academic publications and policy briefs are still in development, dissemination has laid solid groundwork across industrial, scientific, and policy dimensions.

Networking & Collaboration

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Collaboration is integral to INGUMA’s participatory model. A series of **nine co-creation workshops** were conducted, notably during the General Assembly in Thessaloniki (January 2025), where regional stakeholders offered critical feedback (*Figure 20–21*).

Further, INGUMA actively engaged with **sister projects** (e.g., BioBuild, ReConstruct, Woodcircles) to explore clustering synergies and shared knowledge dissemination. These efforts yielded a shared project database and regular online meetings (*Figure 22*).

Conclusion and Outlook

Work Package 6 achieved its primary objective: to establish a communication and collaboration framework that supports awareness, engagement, and future dissemination. While scientific output and exploitation are still maturing, the coming period will see:

- Expanded dissemination of technical results
- Launch of six **product fact sheets** and infographics
- Continued partner interviews and social media campaigns
- Deeper integration with **New European Bauhaus** initiatives

This forward strategy will transition the focus from general awareness to **targeted knowledge transfer, research impact, and policy relevance**.

Table of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
AVG	Average
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
www	World Wide Web
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

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1 Communication Activities

Communication activities in months M1–M18 focused on establishing the most important communication channels, such as the website and LinkedIn, all basic graphic elements, and the first set of communication materials. The results achieved were made possible by the intensive cooperation of all partners. It is important to note that the communication activities were not only successfully implemented through INGUMA's own publication channels. Many partners also disseminated the project activities through their own channels

1.1 Visual Identity & Written Identity

At the start of the project, a comprehensive set of relevant graphic elements was developed based on the communication strategy. The visual design embodies all the important features of the project approach. Above all, the compromise between scientific research and sophisticated architectural design is intended to express the project approach through modern colour selection and minimalist graphic style. The visual identity was tested based on ease of use and various usage scenarios and approved by the project partners. Overall, the visual design comprises the elements of logo, colors, fonts, and templates.

Logo

The logo consists of a graphic element and the project name. The graphic element not only creates a connection between the project name and the visualised building; it also clearly signals the simple and clear orientation of the sustainable and holistic approach to research, development and implementation.

Figure 1 The Inguma logo is a combination of images and words.

Figure 2 Logo variants for different applications.

Project Font

The font was developed based on INGUMA's holistic approach to visual identity design. The SILKA font perfectly rounds off the visual appearance of the project and is used as a graphic tool in all design elements. However, due to its unusual use, the font is not used as a general text font. INGUMA mainly uses Calibri for communication purposes.

Figure 3 Silka – the graphic font of INGUMA.

Template's

For standardised communication, various templates for different application scenarios were designed in the INGUMA project. The templates were developed according to the needs and application scenarios of the partners and agreed upon jointly. In addition to a standard template for creating deliverables, the consortium also has access to a general Word template, a template for invitations to general assemblies, a PowerPoint template, and a pitch deck for general project presentations.

Figure 4 Word Templates.

Figure 5 Power Point Master and Pitch Deck.

1.2 Website

The INGUMA website is graphically based on the visual design concept and clearly reflects the project goals through its minimalist visual approach. When programming the site, we chose a mobile-first approach. Since most access nowadays is via mobile devices, it is important that we cater to this user's behaviour. This means that the content is optimised for viewing on a mobile phone. This can lead to some visual disadvantages in the desktop view.

The website is one of the key communication tools for disseminating all relevant information about INGUMA. Based on the latest digital communication analyses, the INGUMA website is designed as a digital business card that is primarily intended for interested parties who want to consume general content about the project. For this reason, the structure is clear and easy to navigate and is not complicated by numerous subpages and a complex user experience.

The website comprises a central landing page with the most important content in brief, about – all details about the project, Developments – research and development including pilot sites and demo cases, News – INGUMA blog, Events and Downloads, and About us – contact and partners. The central area of the current work on the website is the news page, where articles and the latest events are published regularly.

The website was launched in a basic version in month 4 and updated in month 9.

<https://www.inguma-biobased.eu/>

Figure 6 INGUMA website screenshots (Mobile View).

Table 1 provides an overview of the current website KPIs. The current results show that the INGUMA website is visited regularly. The slight decline in page visits in the first six months of 2025 can be explained by the fact that, following its establishment in 2024, potential visitors are already familiar with the standardised pages, and most traffic is focused on the news section. Basically, it should be noted that we are slightly behind the targets defined in the Grant Agreement. However, with the

increasing duration of the project and regular updates to the website, we can assume that the figures will rise significantly.

Table 1. INGUMA website analytics

	2024	2025
Page Visits	45.597	10.207
Time Spent AVG	224 seconds	127 seconds
Visitors	1.904	1.703
Unique Visitors	1.584	1.426

In addition to establishing INGUMA's own website and publishing numerous articles, INGUMA has also been featured on other platforms over the past 18 months. A total of 11 articles have been published on the internet. The majority of these can be attributed to partner initiatives and are supplemented by announcements of various events.

Table 2 below provides a detailed overview of all publications with the corresponding links.

Table 2. INGUMA mentions on the WWW.

	Content	URL	2025
VTT	Project description	https://cris.vtt.fi/en/projects/reducing-the-footprint-of-consumer-products-through-public-dialog	
FNR	Project description	https://international.fnr.de/project-funding/european-projects/european-projects/inguma	
INNWOOD	Project description	https://innwood.eu/projects/inguma/	
BaskEgur	Project description	https://baskegur.eus/2023/06/19/inguma/	

Certinalia	Article about the 2 nd GA in Thessaloniki	https://certinalia.com/certinalia-participa-en-la-3a-asamblea-general-de-inguma-celebrada-en-thessaloniki-grecia/	
Innovawood	Event announcement	https://innovawood.com/innovawood-shapingsustainablefutures	
Orloga	Project description	https://www.orloga.com/en/inguma-project	
NMP Global Innovation	Report Kick-Off Meeting in Bilbao	https://nmpglobalinnovation.com/2024/01/24/successful-launch-of-project-inguma-kickoff-meeting-on-january-23rd-and-24th-2024-in-bilbao-spain	
EGURTEC	Conference presentation	https://eurtek.bilbaoexhibitioncentre.com/congresos/jornadas-tecnicas/	
FNR	PM Kick-Off Meeting Bilbao	https://international.fnr.de/press/news/project-launch-eu-project-inguma-product-development-based-on-the-values-of-the-new-european-bauhaus-neb	
Atlantis	INGUMA Meeting in Thessaloniki 2 nd GA	https://atlantis-consulting.eu/en/inguma-meeting-summary	

1.3 Social Media

As described in the D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Networking Plan, communication on social networks focused primarily on establishing a solid presence and generating reach on LinkedIn. Following a comprehensive analysis of the target groups, LinkedIn is the key communication channel for the INGUMA project. Both research and industrial environments are very well achieved via this channel, as can be seen from the analyses after the first 18 months. With over 25,000 impressions, over 700 reactions and an engagement rate of just under 25%, the figures are above average for

comparable projects. The responses and engagement are particularly noteworthy here. One identified potential for increasing reach and success on LinkedIn is the number of followers. At 261, this figure is still below expectations after 18 months of the project.

While the activities initially focused on general project information, several campaigns, including one on product development, succeeded in increasing the number of followers and directing interested parties to the INGUMA website.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/inguma-biobased>

Figure 7 Most successful LinkedIn postings during the first 18 month.

Figure 8 LinkedIn INGUMA product development campaign.

The following Table 2 shows the current KPIs for LinkedIn activity over the past 18 months.

Table 3. LinkedIn analytics – KPI's

	No.
Impressions	25.152
Reactions	794
Egagement	24,5%
Postings	42
Followers	261

The demographic structure of INGUMA LinkedIn users clearly shows that the research and development environment is among our most important followers. This is in line with the expectations of the communication measures and fits in with the published content. This means that the communication strategy developed is working and can be continued as set out in the communication plan.

Figure 9 LinkedIn demographic visitors analytics.

1.4 Material

Numerous materials have already been developed in the first 18 months to ensure consistent and sustainable communication and dissemination of the INGUMA project. In addition to the basic elements, such as roll-ups, brochures and posters, individual versions have been adapted or supplemented with additional materials to meet the specific needs of the partners.

The six-page folded project brochure is particularly noteworthy. It follows the visual concept of the project design and, in terms of both form and content, is a product that clearly underscores the

project approach. The brochure has already been printed and used for various occasions (co-creation workshops, trade fairs and conferences).

INGUMA generally follows the European Commission's sustainability recommendations and only prints communication materials at the request of its partners. The aim is to carry out as many communication tasks as possible digitally

Figure 10 INGUMA Roll-Up and Poster.

Figure 11 INGUMA Project Brochure.

1.5 Content

The creation of relevant communication content began intensively in month 6 of the project. The focus of content creation was on publication on the website blog and on social media. A total of 12 articles and 1 press release were published in the first 18 months.

The articles clearly reflect the diversity of topics covered by the project communication. They range from reporting on events relevant to INGUMA (General Assembly, workshops, conferences, etc.) to the start of a series of journalistic interviews with the project partners. The aim of these interviews is to disseminate individual professional perspectives on the project approach and its development, thereby sharing exciting insights.

The following website links provide you with all available content for download as well as direct access to the latest blog posts:

<https://www.inguma-biobased.eu/news-events/>

Figure 12 INGUMA Press Releases.

Figure 13 INGUMA Articles and Interviews.

1.6 Facts & Figures

The following paragraph deals with the goals achieved so far as set out in the Grant Agreement. In summary, it can be said that we have largely achieved the expected goals for the first 18 months with all communication activities. In addition to the standard setup at the beginning of the project, we have also succeeded in establishing supplementary communication activities at an early stage. All facts are documented in Table 03 below.

Table 4. Facts & Figures Communication Activities

	Description	Expected Result	Current Result
Visual Identity	Logo and visual identity (brand), Word and PowerPoint templates	1 visual identity, 4 templates	4 Templates
Communication Package	Brochure, roll-up banner, poster, social media visuals, standard presentation, key messages and written identity	1 of each	Done
Website	Dedicated project website compiling all project information, reports, outputs and general information	20,000 page views	
Media Kit	Press releases for key milestones, partner interviews/feature articles available via project website	At least 8 press releases & 8 interviews/feature articles	2 Press releases 1 Partner interview/feature article
Social Media	Twitter, LinkedIn and ResearchGate pages to raise awareness of the project, its results & potential impacts	2,000 followers across platforms	261

1.7 What's Next

Looking back on the first 18 months of communication activities, we have achieved our initial goal of disseminating and raising awareness of the INGUMA project. However, communication activities will be significantly stepped up again in the coming months.

The focus will then be on communicating and disseminating the developed products and their upscaling. To this end, a product campaign is planned on websites and on social media platforms. This will be supported by dedicated communication material (creating fact sheets including results and lessons learned from the development process).

The second important activity is the creation of an infographic that refers to the holistic approach of the INGUMA project. This infographic will be used digitally and as a poster. The content will follow a modular approach. This means that the graphics will be designed so that they can also be used individually for different presentation requirements without additional effort. The partner interview series is also set to continue. Three more interviews are scheduled to be published in 2025.

2 Dissemination Activities

During the first 18 months, the dissemination of the INGUMA project was not given the same focus as communication. Based on the communication and dissemination plan from month 6, the strategic orientation was largely adhered to and the dissemination of results and initial findings was stepped up, particularly at the start of the second project year. Important highlights of the first 18 months definitely include the participation of our partners FNR and Chimar in the LIGNA Conference 2025 in Hanover. As well as the participation of our partner LUKE in the 3rd edition of 'International Drivers for Wood Construction' in Finland in 2024.

Another significant dissemination milestone was the cooperation initiated by our partner Innovawood for the final event of the New European Bauhaus projects Nebula B4P and CrAFT - Creating an Actionable Future. In addition, Tecnalía achieved a successful impact in a workshop in 2024 on the integration of global project partners.

2.1 Industrial Dissemination

Industrial dissemination was mainly characterised by participation in leading international conferences in the wood industry. As a result, the initiative launched by partner BaskEgur achieved significant dissemination in its first year. In October 2024, one of the region's most important international trade fairs and conferences, EGURTEK, took place in Bilbao. This event is a meeting place for architects and technical developers from the wood industry. During a panel discussion at this event, Aitor Barrio had the opportunity to present the project to a relevant target audience.

<https://egurtek.bilbaoexhibitioncentre.com/congreso/jornadas-tecnicas/#single/0>

Figure 14 Impressions of the Egurtek Conference and Fair 2024.

Other initiatives was the participation of our Finnish partner LUKE in the 3rd edition of “International Drivers for Wood Construction” in Finland in February 2025. An extensive project presentation and intensive exchange with the target group provided valuable insights for further project development.

<https://www.inguma-biobased.eu/joensuu-in-finland-hotspot-of-the-innovative-wood-industry/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7295703929953083392>

Figure 15 Dissemination and communication of the conference Participation by LUKE in Finland.

An even more milestone in industrial dissemination was participation in one of Europe's largest wood industry conferences, Ligna 2025 in Hanover. INGUMA was well represented by its Greek project partner CHIMAR and its German partner FNR. Both trade fair appearances were accompanied by INGUMA communication materials. In addition, FNR organised a co-creation workshop for the German timber industry, where the bi-directional exchange once again yielded valuable insights.

<https://www.inguma-biobased.eu/cross-disciplinary-cooperation-in-shaping-the-future-of-construction/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7336437043859718144>

Figure 16 Dissemination and communication Ligna 2025.

Initiated by our project partner Innovawood, the INGUMA project became part of a sustainable event in March 2025. The final event organised by Nebula B4P and CRAFT in Brussels provided a platform for a workshop on the most important topics of the INGUMA project. An intensive discussion about the potential of biomaterials in the construction sector also yielded valuable insights for both sides. Participants from the fields of research, development and industry in particular clearly expressed their current and future needs.

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7306292062558019585>

<https://www.inguma-biobased.eu/workshop-insights-climate-conscious-construction-on-the-rise/>

Figure 17 Workshop final event Nebula B4P.

The following table 5 contains an overview of all event participations of all partners in the past 18 months.

Table 5. Overview INGUMA participation all industrial events and conferences.

	EVENT	Format	Target Group	Participants
LUKE	2025 Drivers for Woodconstruction (Joensuu) “Future Green Cities Fostering Growth Based on Wood”	Project Presentation	Wood Construction Industry and Research	>500
FNR	2025 LIGNA (Hanover) Congress & Exposition	Booth representation Co-Creation Workshop	German and International Wood Industry	>1.000 25 participants of the Workshop
CHIMAR	2025 LIGNA (Hanover) Congress & Exposition	Booth representation	International Wood Industry	

TECNALIA / Bas	2024 EGURTEK (Bilbao) Congress & Expositon	Project PPT	Architects and Technical Wood Industry	1300
Innovawood	2025 Shaping Sustainable Futures (Brussels)	Workshop	European Projects Industry Research and Development New European Bauhaus	100

2.2 Scientific Dissemination

As already defined in the communication and dissemination plan, scientific dissemination is based on significant research results. Since these always emerge in the course of development, the activity in this task was defined as rather low. However, it is planned to intensify this activity at the beginning of the next reporting period and to publish the first scientific papers.

However, there was a noteworthy initiative regarding international scientific cooperation with our Canadian partner from Quebec, Laval University.

INGUMA project partner and coordinator TECNALIA ensured an important start to scientific dissemination. At the invitation of the global initiative EURAXESS - researchers in motion, the focus was on discussing continental cooperation with Canadian partner Laval University and its potential. The webinar took place in the second half of 2024 and marked the beginning of a long-term cooperation for the exchange of experiences in the integration of global research partners in Horizon Europe-funded research projects.

<https://www.inguma-biobased.eu/support-non-european-entities-in-horizon-europe/>

Figure 18 Webinar of EURAXESS initiative.

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The following Table 6 provides an overview of the potential ideas for possible scientific publications. The initial idea is to publish one per task of WP1.

Table 6. Overview INGUMA ideas for possible scientific publications.

Partner	Topic	Year of Publication
CHIMAR	Bio-based adhesives and recycling-friendly plywood panels	2026-2027
VTT	Lignocellulosic fibres from side-streams	2026-2027
TECNALIA	Resin-free lignocellulosic fibers-based thermal insulation board	2026-2027
LUKE	Mycelial based insulation board	2026-2027
LUKE	Wood side streams-based substrates for vegetated roofs	2026-2027

2.3 Policy Dissemination

Similar requirements apply to policy dissemination as to scientific dissemination. The actual work on this task will not begin until the second reporting period of the project. However, there was a noteworthy initiative by the European Commission, more specifically Cluster 6, in May 2025. At the invitation of the EC, INGUMA had the opportunity to participate in a workshop with 13 other Cluster 6 projects and engage in an intensive exchange with numerous project officers and the policy officer on the topics of biobased innovation, biotechnology, life sciences, and digital solutions.

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7329025518375165952>

Figure 19 Cluster 6 Workshop Brussels.

2.4 Facts and Figures

About the objectives achieved in Task 6.3, it can be said that the foundations for disseminating the project have been laid out. With six presentations and participation in international events, the project partners are on target. The focus on dissemination in the industrial environment is in line with the holistic approach and the aim of attracting attention in the construction sector.

Table 7. Overview all dissemination KPI's

	Description	Expected Result	Current Result
Scientific and technical publications	Publication of project results in peer-reviewed scientific journals and technical publications	8 Articles or Publications	-
Presentation in conferences and events	Technical presentation of project results in scientific and industry events	20	6
Policy brief and recommendations	Policy brief looking at the regulatory bottlenecks to uptake of sustainable construction materials, and a set of recommendations to overcome them	1	-
Final Conference	A final conference will be held (Brussels, or suitable industry forum) to bring final results and policy messages to end-users.	80 participants	-
End product social media campaign	Citizens and end-users will be informed about the impacts of bio-based construction materials via a dedicated social media campaign and infographics.	6 Infographics	-
Webinars	Webinars in the final year, presenting results, conclusions, and products to all audiences.	3 webinars/ 200 views	-
Demonstrator Videos	Twitter, LinkedIn and ResearchGate pages to raise awareness of the project, its results & potential impacts	2 Videos / 800 Views	-
Fact Sheets	A description of the different products developed by INGUMA, including information on socio-economic and environmental benefits.	6 fact sheets developed	-

2.5 What's Next

Following the groundwork laid in the first 18 months, the focus of dissemination activities in the coming months will be on increasing participation in further relevant events and verifying the first academic papers. In principle, the dissemination target group is to be expanded to include science and research, and appropriate measures are being planned.

With the start of the creation of the six fact sheets, it should be possible to familiarise researchers and innovators with the INGUMA project, particularly at academic events. There are also plans to intensify the exchange and integration of the New European Bauhaus Initiative. The aim is to develop one or two viable concepts in the coming months that will support dissemination in the long term.

3 Networking & Collaboration

Networking and collaboration were important factors in spreading the project idea and initiating intensive cooperation with external stakeholders during the first 18 months. Collaboration and co-creation are one of the cornerstones of the INGUMA project. The early start of this initiative ensured a solid basis for building a relevant INGUMA network. Specific partners for specific challenges. The collaboration in more than nine workshops over the past 18 months has had a lasting impact on development.

However, it was not only possible to establish cooperation with external experts for the sustainable promotion of product development. In the second half of 2024, INGUMA, together with its sister projects BioBuild, Reconstruct and Woodcircles, launched a series of online meetings to verify joint potential in numerous dimensions of cooperation.

3.1 Co-Creation Workshops

The nine co-creation workshops from work package 2 played a decisive role in networking and collaboration activities during the first 18 months. They are a cornerstone of the INGUMA project and represent milestones in its development in terms of networking and collaboration.

The early timing of the first project year has had a lasting impact on the establishment of long-term networking and collaboration activities.

For work package 6, this means that we will continue to involve external experts from the respective workshops in our various networking initiatives. It should already be noted that the impact has contributed to the dissemination and acceptance of the project approach. However, due to the confidential nature of the content, intensive reporting was not possible.

To underline the impact once again, the workshop at the General Assembly in Thessaloniki in January 2025 should be mentioned here. Fifteen local and regional participants from research, science and industry spent more than four hours intensively examining the INGUMA project and its approaches. They provided us and our partners with valuable feedback on the needs in the relevant areas and critically questioned several issues. All further information on the co-creation workshops can be found in Deliverable 2.3

Figure 20 Co-Creation Workshop in Thessaloniki.

Figure 21 Co-Creation Workshop LinkedIn post reached more than 2000 Impression and 810 clicks.

3.2 Cluster Initiative Sister Projects

The Sister Project collaboration is characterised by very intensive exchange between the three sister projects and an extended circle of projects with a view to establishing a cluster. In more than four meetings, a small database was created containing all the important facts about the participating projects and their activities. For INGUMA, however, the focus is less on membership in the planned cluster. From the perspective of the INGUMA project, the focus is rather on the efficient design of joint measures and the fundamental exchange of experience from research and development. In the coming months, it is planned to discuss the knowledge gained so far from research and development in a larger circle of all sister projects.

<https://www.inguma-biobased.eu/a-perfect-start-for-a-sustainable-collaboration/>

Figure 22 Sister project collaboration.

3.3 What's Next

In the Networking and Collaboration task, following the groundwork laid in the first 18 months, the aim is now to expand cooperation and exploit the potential with sister projects. Initially, this will focus on communication, but will also include the exchange of initial development findings. The goal is to leverage the expert knowledge of all relevant network partners to steer the project even more efficiently and with greater impact in the coming months.

Other networking and collaboration activities also include investment in cooperation with the New European Bauhaus Initiative. Initial discussions have already taken place with the Sleeping Beauty project, which was launched in May, and similar European initiatives.

4 Conclusion

After 18 months of project work, it can be said that Work Package 6 has achieved solid results. However, it should be noted that the work and impact primarily relate to general communication activities and that only a small amount of validated results have been shared with the public.

It is therefore important that the focus in the coming weeks and months shifts primarily to the communication and dissemination of initial research and development results. To this end, all partners involved in these tasks are requested to provide the most important findings for communication and dissemination.

In addition, greater attention should be paid to scientific dissemination. The early development of relevant academic topics will help to raise awareness of the project among the relevant target group in the coming project period and enable long-term work with the scientific results in various areas.

In general, the focus of the work package will shift from pure communication to dissemination and exploitation. Work in the area of exploitation has already begun through cooperation with work package 2, but has not yet had a significant impact on task 6.4.

In terms of communication, the implementation of the measures defined in the Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan v1 will be continued. This will include further journalistic interviews and articles on the website and social media. The expansion of social media activities to include Research Gate, among others, is also being considered.

5 Annex

No Annex document in regarding the deliverable.

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